

Utilisation of Information Communication Technology in Cataloguing and Classification Practices in Federal University Libraries in North East, Nigeria

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Abstract

Purpose: The purpose of the study is to determine Information Communication Technology Utilisation in Cataloguing and classification Practices in Federal University Libraries in North-East, Nigeria.

Methodology: A Descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The study population consisted of 399 librarians and para-professional librarians from the six federal university libraries in the North-Eastern region of Nigeria. The study employed a sample size of 399, using the census sampling technique. The research instrument used in the study was a questionnaire, titled "Utilisation of Information Communication Technology Cataloguing and Classification Routines Questionnaire" (UICTCCPQ). The questionnaire employed a four-point rating scale. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to answer the research questions. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient was also used to test the null hypothesis formulated at the .05 level of significance.

Findings: Based on the findings, there is a low relationship between ICT utilisation and cataloguing and classification routines in federal university libraries in the North East, Nigeria. Also, Inadequate funding, inadequate ICT facilities, inadequate library software package, lack of encouragement from the management, poor maintenance culture, inadequate training of staff on ICT, staff apathy to ICT, lack of vendor technical support, and poor Internet connectivity are factors hindering ICT utilisation for effective cataloguing and classification routines in Federal University libraries in North East, Nigeria.

Conclusion/Recommendations: It was recommended that librarians in federal university libraries in North-East, Nigeria should use ICT for effective cataloguing and classification Practices when the ICT facilities are provided. Furthermore, the management of the libraries under study should adequately address all the factors hindering ICT utilisation for successful cataloguing and classification practices within the libraries.

Study Type: Empirical.

Keywords: Information, Communication, Technology, Utilisation, Cataloguing and Classification and Routines

Introduction

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has demonstrated its profound impact on library systems, services, and operations, particularly in cataloguing and classification. ICT ensures the easy integration of various library activities, increasing efficiency in acquisition, cataloguing, classification, data access, and information retrieval and dissemination. It enhances data storage, data and full-text searching, eliminates uninteresting and repetitive work, helps avoid duplication of efforts, increases the range of services, facilitates cooperation and the formation of networks and resource sharing in libraries, among other benefits. ICT

encompasses the internet, wireless networks, cell phones, computers, software, video conferencing, social networking, and other media applications and services, enabling users to access, retrieve, store, transmit, and manipulate information in digital form. Similarly, ICT is also used to refer to the convergence of media technology, such as audio-visual and telephone networks, with computer networks, through a unified system of cabling or a link system (Murray, 2018). There are large economic incentives to merge the telephone network with the computer network system using a single unified system of cabling and signal distribution. ICT is an umbrella term that encompasses any communication device, including radio, television, cell phones, computer and network hardware, satellite systems, and various services and appliances such as video conferencing and distance learning (Kondra, 2020). It encompasses any product that stores, retrieves, manipulates, transmits, or receives information electronically, such as personal computers, including smartphones, as well as television and email (Ozdamli et al., 2015).

The use of ICT in the library has significantly transformed the working environment. The emergence of automation software and its applications has brought about a major shift in library operations and functions, moving from being traditionally heavily dependent on human labour to managing core activities through technology. This exemplifies what ICT utilisation can achieve. The level of ICT use varies among libraries; some employ it for all routine tasks, while others use it selectively to enhance information services for users. Implementing ICT improves library routines for efficient information delivery. In an era where users demand quick and easy access to information, ICT is essential for streamlining library operations. ICT utilisation also contributes to the sustainable development of the nation, as timely and effective access to useful information helps build a stronger society. As an enabling tool, ICT supports libraries in providing vital information, which is crucial for the development of various sectors in the country (Shariful and Nazmul, 2016). Libraries that utilise ICT play a vital role in facilitating access to global knowledge and information resources. Aina et al. (2014) described ICT as the ability to access information using telecommunication-based internet resources. ICT enables the creation, organisation, manipulation, and access of information from remote locations worldwide, within a short time frame. It involves integrating various technologies to support the acquisition, processing, storage, and dissemination of information in libraries. Continuous advances in ICT have profoundly changed how information is acquired, processed, stored, retrieved, and communicated (Elisha, 2016), thereby significantly influencing library activities.

Cataloguing and classification routines ensure the proper preparation of materials for library use through sorting, cataloguing, and classifying the materials, as well as filing index cards, labeling call numbers on each document's spine, and dispatching materials to appropriate library locations for easy access. This makes cataloguing and classification a processing unit where decisions about organising information resources are made by the cataloguers. These processes serve to organise library resources, making it easier for users to access and retrieve information. According to Akidi and Omekwu (2016), cataloguing and classification are the central nervous system of librarianship, emphasising that they are not ends in themselves but foundational for providing information to users. Proper organisation of sources allows users to find specific documents easily among the vast array of resources available. The goal of cataloguing and classification is to ensure timely and effective access for easy utilisation of information resources. Atinmo (2013) stated that these practices are interrelated activities within the library that assist users in locating and selecting relevant information resources for study and research. There are two complementary bibliographic control practices carried out

by cataloguers to facilitate easy access and resource location: cataloguing involves the physical description of library resources, while classification involves making decisions on subject analysis, determining relevant subjects, and assigning suitable class numbers or call marks. This arrangement ensures that resources are organised by class number, making retrieval straightforward. Overall, cataloguing and classification enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of library activities.

Statement of the Problem

The utilisation of ICT facilities such as computers, scanning machines, barcode readers, library software, internet library websites, and storage devices like hard drives has the potential to make information storage, processing, and delivery more effective and efficient within the library. Utilising ICT enhances cataloguing and classification practices, allowing for easier processing of books, serials, and other non-book materials. It replaces the manually operated library system, which is less efficient in processing and providing the correct information to the right user at the right time. To illustrate the benefits of ICT utilisation in the library, books and non-book materials can be catalogued electronically, library users can access these catalogues online, and the acquisition of books and serials can also be managed using ICT. According to researchers' observations, ICT facilities are available in federal university libraries across Northeast Nigeria. However, are librarians utilising these ICT facilities effectively for cataloguing and classification practices in these libraries? It is against this background that the study aims to determine the utilisation of ICT in cataloguing and classification practices in federal university libraries in North-East Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What is the relationship between the Utilisation of ICT in cataloguing and classification practices in Federal University libraries in North East, Nigeria?
2. What are the Factors hindering the utilisation of ICT for effective cataloguing and classification in Federal University libraries in North East, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

This null hypothesis was formulated to guide the study:

H1. There is no significant relationship between the Utilisation of ICT in cataloguing and classification routines in federal university libraries in the North East, Nigeria.

Literature Review

This study is based on the Technology Acceptance Theory proposed by Davis (1989), as outlined by Korpelainen (2011). The theory suggests that the success of a system depends on user acceptance, which is measured by three factors: perceived usefulness (PU), perceived ease of use (PEOU), and attitude towards use (ATU) of the system. According to Technology Acceptance Theory, an individual's actual use of a technology system is directly or indirectly influenced by their behavioural intentions, attitude, perceived usefulness, and perceived ease of use. The theory also states that external factors impact intention and actual use through mediated effects on perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use.

Figure 1 Technology Acceptance Theories (Davis, 1989)

Perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness of technology are factors that influence user attitude towards technology, subsequent behavioural intentions, and actual usage. In reality, perceived ease of use is also thought to affect perceived usefulness of the technology. Both perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use shape users' attitudes towards technology utilisation. Perceived usefulness (PU) is the extent to which a person believes that using technology will improve their job performance, while Perceived Ease of Use (PE) is the extent to which a person believes that using a particular system will require minimal effort. Certain environmental factors also influence a user's decision to adopt or use technology. These include the availability of infrastructure to support adoption, accessibility to the technology, and perceptions of its usefulness. These, among other factors, are classified as external variables in this theory.

This theory is relevant to the study as perceived usefulness relates to the ICT utilisation for effective cataloguing and classification routines, in the sense that until library staff accept that ICT is useful for their daily operations, they cannot fully utilise it to enhance their services. Similarly, perceived ease of use depends on the utilisation of ICT. That means until ICT is available and library staff are trained, awareness about the technology cannot be effectively created. After training, they will recognise that the new system is easy to use, which will enable them to use it efficiently to improve cataloguing and classification routines.

Cataloguing involves bibliographic description, subject analysis, assignment of classification notation, and all activities involved in physically preparing the item to be placed on the shelf. This task is usually performed under the supervision of a librarian trained as a cataloguer. According to Aina (2004), cataloguing consists of two parts: descriptive cataloguing and subject cataloguing. Descriptive cataloguing entails providing bibliographic details using the elements available in the information resource to be described, guided by the choice of access points. The elements used in bibliographic description include the author, title, edition, place of publication, publisher's name, date of publication, International Standard Book Number (ISBN) for books, and International Standard Serial Number (ISSN) for serial publications. Through cataloguing, individual items are made unique from other items. To maintain international standards, descriptive cataloguing is carried out using the Anglo-American Cataloguing Rules, second edition (AACR2), which is gradually being replaced by Resource Description and Access (RDA) in this digital age. Libraries, mainly in developed countries, have begun using RDA instead of AACR2 in their cataloguing practices, as noted by John-Okeke (2013). Supporting this, Aina and Onuoha (2016) stated that many national libraries, such as the British Library, Library of Congress, National Library of Australia, National Library

of Singapore, National Library of Malaysia, and National Library of the Philippines, are adopting Resource Description and Access (RDA) in their cataloguing processes.

Online cataloguing involves using bibliographic information stored in bibliographic utilities or online catalogues. It is derived from copy cataloguing. Nwosu (2015) stated that online cataloguing and classification on the web have improved cataloguers' work output as library resources are processed more quickly with appropriate software. Cataloguers who catalogue online often make modifications specific to their own library needs. However, since many national publications are not available online, original cataloguing remains essential. Burman (2017) advised cataloguers at the University of California, Los Angeles, to adhere to stricter quality standards than copy cataloguing because original records are shared with thousands of other libraries. Another form of online cataloguing involves using other libraries' online public access catalogues (OPACS) for cataloguing and classification activities. OPAC is a computerised library catalogue. Calhoun (2016) described it as a database of bibliographic records that detail the information resources in a library, accessible to the public via public terminals. With the advent of the Internet, most libraries have made their OPACS accessible from servers to users and other libraries worldwide. The author also noted that, due to the display of call numbers through OPAC, it has become a standard method of bibliographic access globally, and databases are built based on it. As a result, the WWW has enabled libraries to make their catalogues freely available to a wider audience and use them as online cataloguing tools for cataloguers, thereby improving bibliographic control. Outsourcing involves contracting library services that were previously performed in-house to an external service provider, often a profit-making enterprise. While opinions about outsourcing vary, Edem and Ntui (2012) observed that it is necessary when there is a backlog of resources to catalogue and can be useful during accreditation processes in academic libraries. Outsourcing may also be employed during the processing of resources for national bibliographies or when funds are insufficient to employ permanent staff. The author, however, suggested that outsourcing cataloguing practices should not become routine in the library profession, to avoid compromising professionalism.

The study by Akidi and Okezie (2018) examined the application of information and communication technology (ICT) to cataloguing and classification for effective bibliographic control, focusing on the National Library of Nigeria as the country's bibliographic control agency. Six objectives guided the research. The adopted research design was a survey method. The population consisted of 33 cataloguers, and the sampling technique involved a complete census of all cataloguers at the National Library of Nigeria (NLN), as the population was manageable. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire with forty-two items divided into six clusters. Data analysis employed statistical tools, including frequency tables, percentages, means, and standard deviations. The findings showed that the NLN extensively adopts various cataloguing practices, including quality, original, copy, and centralised cataloguing, while online cataloguing and outsourcing are not utilised. Additionally, the study revealed that the NLN's overall effectiveness in applying ICT to cataloguing and classification is low. Concerning library software packages, only CDS-ISIS was widely used. Regarding ICT knowledge and skills, cataloguers demonstrated high proficiency in computer and internet skills, but showed low proficiency in other areas, and their application of ICT knowledge and skills to cataloguing and classification was also limited. The challenges faced in applying ICT to cataloguing and classification included inadequate funding, insufficient infrastructural facilities, inconsistent power supply, lack of internet access and bandwidth, limited vendor technical support, poor maintenance culture, and inadequate staff training.

The study recommended that the National Library of Nigeria should adopt online cataloguing alongside other methods to reduce backlogs; that cataloguers should improve their ICT application skills; that the NLN should implement and seek support for library software packages; that the Nigerian federal government should enhance funding for the NLN; and that the NLN should efficiently utilise available funds to acquire and maintain ICT infrastructure, ensure a reliable power supply, establish internet facilities with sufficient bandwidth, and facilitate regular staff training on ICT skills. The study concluded that applying ICT to cataloguing and classification significantly improves bibliographic control, emphasising the necessity for the NLN to address any obstacles hindering ICT implementation in these areas. The study is related to the present research because both focus on library routines and ICT utilisation in libraries—the two studies employed survey research methods and questionnaires as research instruments. However, a difference is observed in the research areas. The reviewed study was conducted at the National Library of Nigeria, whereas the current study was carried out in the federal university libraries in North East Nigeria.

Whong and Zakari (2014) examined the utilisation of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) for library routines in selected Nigerian federal university libraries. The study employed a survey research method, selecting six academic libraries from federal universities across Nigeria's six geopolitical zones. Area or cluster probability sampling was used. The questionnaire was the instrument for data collection. A total of 336 (92.3%) copies of the questionnaire were duly completed and returned, making them usable for this study. Data were analysed descriptively; to further clarify the study, the researchers interviewed one staff member from each of the selected academic libraries. The study found that ICT facilities are frequently used in cataloguing and classification of information resources, scoring 250 (74%), and in the selection of information resources, scoring 244 (73%), while statistical records had the lowest score at 44%. Computers were the most often used ICT facilities in the libraries studied. Advances in ICT have significantly enhanced information provision, not only in the selection, ordering, acquisition, processing, storage, and retrieval of library resources but also in improving staff productivity. It is expected that Nigerian federal university libraries (NFUL) can fully utilise and benefit from ICT facilities, especially in digitising local content, establishing institutional repositories, and maintaining functional websites. The challenges of ICT utilisation, if improperly managed, could reduce the libraries' potential to achieve the goals and objectives of their parent institutions. The study recommended that NFUL should adopt open-source library management software, DSpace content management system, and document management systems to enhance library operations. This study relates to the present one, as both focus on the utilisation of ICT for effective library routines. Both studies employed survey research methods and questionnaires as research instruments. They differ in scope; the former covered selected federal university libraries across Nigeria's six geopolitical zones, while the present study focuses on federal university libraries in the North-East zone.

Methods

This study employed a descriptive survey research design because it involves using a sample and questionnaires to gather data from respondents. This design is also appropriate because the study aims to establish relationships between two variables, with data being collected, coded, and analysed. The variables of interest are the utilisation of ICT and cataloguing and classification practices in federal university libraries in North-East Nigeria. The population comprised 141 librarians and 258 para-professional librarians across six federal university libraries in North-East Nigeria. The entire population of 399 was sampled using a census

method. The scores obtained from respondents were analysed using Cronbach's Alpha to test the instrument's reliability. A reliability coefficient of 0.82 was achieved, indicating the instrument was reliable for data collection. Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation was used to address the research questions and test the hypotheses. A total of 399 questionnaires were distributed to librarians and para-professional librarians in federal university libraries in the North-East region of Nigeria. Of these, 390 questionnaires were retrieved, resulting in a response rate of 97.7%. Only properly completed and returned questionnaires were included in the analysis.

Results and Discussion

The result of the data analysis carried out on the data collected for the study is presented as follows:

Research Question 1

What is the relationship between the utilisation of ICT in cataloguing and classification practices in Federal University libraries in the North East, Nigeria?

Table 1: Summary of analysis on the relationship between utilisation of ICT in cataloguing and classification practices in federal university libraries in North East, Nigeria (n = 390)

Variables	$\sum X$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum XY$	r-value
	$\sum Y$	$\sum Y^2$		
Utilisation of ICT	2936	22856	29180	0.20
Cataloguing and classification practices	3856	38880		

The result presented in Table 1 showed an r-value of 0.20, indicating a weak relationship between the utilisation of ICT in cataloguing and classification practices in federal university libraries in North East, Nigeria. This finding suggests that there is a limited association between the utilisation of ICT in these practices. The significance of this is that ICT utilisation can make cataloguing and classification faster and more efficient; for example, bibliographic searches become easier, cataloguing and classification can be duplicated, and the library catalogue can be organised through OPAC. All of these improvements are achieved through the utilisation of ICT.

Research Question 2

What are the factors hindering the utilisation of ICT for effective cataloguing and classification practices in Federal University libraries in the North East, Nigeria?

Table 2: Summary of mean and standard deviation scores of the factors hindering utilisation of ICT for effective cataloguing and classification practices in Federal University libraries in North East, Nigeria

S/N	Factors hindering the utilisation of ICT for effective cataloguing and classification practices in Federal University libraries in North East, Nigeria	\bar{x}	SD	Remarks
1.	Inadequate funding	3.53	0.63	Strongly Agreed
2.	Inadequate ICT facilities	3.29	0.62	Agreed
3.	Inadequate power supply	2.30	0.61	Disagreed
4.	Inadequate library software package	3.04	0.54	Agreed
5.	Lack of encouragement from the management	3.11	0.57	Agreed
6	Poor maintenance culture	3.16	0.59	Agreed
7	Inadequate training of staff on ICT	3.09	0.60	Agreed
8	Staff apathy to ICT	2.97	0.59	Agreed
9	Lack of vendor technical support	3.04	0.56	Agreed

10	Poor Internet connectivity	2.78	0.69	Agreed
	Cluster Mean	3.03	0.60	Agreed

The result in Table 2 revealed the mean range for the response of the respondents on factors hindering utilisation of ICT for effective cataloguing and classification practices in Federal University libraries in North East, Nigeria for items 2,4,5,6,7,8,9 and 10 falls within 2.50-3.49 which means that the respondents agreed that inadequate ICT facilities, inadequate library software package, lack of encouragement from the management, poor maintenance culture, inadequate training of staff on ICT, staff apathy to ICT, lack of vendor technical support and poor Internet connectivity are factors hindering utilisation of ICT for effective library routines in Federal University libraries in North East, Nigeria. The result in Table 2 also revealed that the mean range of the respondents for item 3 falls within 1.00-1.49, which means that the respondents disagreed that inadequate power supply is a factor hindering the utilisation of ICT for effective cataloguing and classification practices in Federal University libraries in North East, Nigeria. The results in Table 2 further reveal that the mean range of the respondents for item 1 falls within 3.50-4.00, indicating that the respondents strongly agreed that inadequate funding is a factor hindering the utilisation of ICT for effective cataloguing and classification practices in Federal University libraries in North East, Nigeria. However, the cluster mean of 3.03 for all the items implies that inadequate funding, inadequate ICT facilities, inadequate library software package, lack of encouragement from the management, poor maintenance culture, inadequate training of staff on ICT, staff apathy to ICT, lack of vendor technical support and poor Internet connectivity are factors hindering ICT utilisation of ICT for effective cataloguing and classification practices in Federal University libraries in North East, Nigeria.

Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between the utilisation of ICT in cataloguing and classification practices in federal university libraries in the North East, Nigeria.

*Significant at .05 level, df = 388

Table 3: Summary of Pearson Product-Moment Correlation analysis on the relationship between utilisation of ICT in cataloguing and classification practices in federal university libraries in North East, Nigeria (n = 390).

Variables	$\sum X$	$\sum X^2$	$\sum XY$	r-cal	r-cit	Decision
Utilisation of ICT	2936	22856	29180	0.20	.113	Significant
Cataloguing and classification practices	3856	38880				

The results in Table 3 indicate that the calculated r-value of 0.20 exceeds the critical r-value of .113 at the .05 level of significance with 388 degrees of freedom. Based on this, the null hypothesis was rejected. This suggests there is a significant relationship between the utilisation of ICT in cataloguing and classification practices in federal university libraries in North East, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The analysis of the research questions concerning the relationship between ICT utilisation and cataloguing and classification routines in federal university libraries in North East Nigeria

revealed a weak correlation between ICT use and these routines. However, the hypothesis test indicated a significant relationship between ICT utilisation and cataloguing and classification routines in these libraries. This disparity arises because only a few librarians utilise ICT facilities such as computers and the Internet for copy cataloguing and classification, mainly due to insufficient ICT resources and a lack of staff training in ICT. Proper utilisation of ICT can improve bibliographic searching, cataloguing, classification, and information resource filing, making these processes faster and easier. This finding contrasts with that of Whong and Zakari (2014), who observed that ICT facilities were frequently used in cataloguing and classification, with scores of 250 (74%) and 244 (73%), respectively, while statistical records scored the lowest at 44%. Computers were identified as the most commonly used ICT tools in the studied library. Advances in ICT have significantly enhanced not only the selection, ordering, acquisition, processing, storage, and retrieval of library resources but also staff productivity. The finding aligns with the study by Akidi and Okezie (2018), which noted low effectiveness of the National Library of Nigeria (NLN) in applying ICT to its cataloguing and classification practices. Similarly, Mamman (2015) found that ICT usage in Nigerian public libraries is generally low for everyday operations but more prominent in library administration, management, and accessing online resources.

The analysis of factors hindering ICT utilisation for effective cataloguing and classification routines in Federal University libraries in North East Nigeria revealed that inadequate funding, insufficient ICT facilities, an inadequate library software package, lack of encouragement from management, poor maintenance culture, insufficient staff training on ICT, staff apathy towards ICT, lack of vendor technical support, and poor Internet connectivity are major barriers. This is due to insufficient funding and a lack of interest from management in addressing these challenges facing federal university libraries in North-East Nigeria. The findings support Rosenberg's (2015) observation that the challenges of ICT utilisation include a lack of library software standardisation, insufficient security measures to prevent theft, and erratic power supply in most Nigerian university libraries. Additionally, the findings align with Okiy's (2015) report highlighting poor and inadequate telecommunication facilities, low levels of computer literacy, absence of a functional ICT policy, resistance to change, limited communication infrastructure, lack of policies for manpower development, low awareness of Internet facilities among policymakers, government officials, and the ruling class, as well as minimal involvement of academic institutions in network building in Africa as hurdles to ICT use in libraries. Furthermore, the findings support Gardner's (2019) assertion that inadequate human resources, poor maintenance, limited funding, and insufficient training are significant factors affecting the utilisation of ICT in developing countries.

Conclusion

The use of ICT enhances cataloguing and classification methods, leading to improved service delivery in libraries. It eliminates boring and repetitive tasks, helps prevent duplicated efforts, and fosters cooperation, networking, and resource sharing among librarians across different libraries. Although ICT use is important for efficient cataloguing and classification, most cataloguers in federal university libraries in North East Nigeria still perform their tasks manually. According to the study's findings, there is a low correlation between ICT use and cataloguing and classification practices in these libraries. This indicates that librarians in these institutions do not fully utilise the available ICT resources for effective cataloguing and classification. The reasons include insufficient funding, limited ICT infrastructure, a lack of suitable library software, inadequate support from management, poor maintenance habits, insufficient staff training in ICT, staff indifference to ICT, the absence of vendor technical

support, and poor Internet connectivity. Library management should tackle these challenges to promote successful ICT-driven cataloguing and classification routines. It is also hoped that librarians, especially cataloguers, will seize the opportunity, once resources are sufficiently provided, to enhance cataloguing practices.

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